

RIGHTS AND MAINTENANCE OF THE PARENTS AND SENIOR CITIZENS: A SOCIO-LEGAL STUDY

by

Gazala Noor

Ph.D. Research scholar

Jammu University, Law Department

ABSTRACT

“This research paper will look at an important concern in our culture: the challenges that the aged face and the reasons for them, as well as a variety of government services and rights for the senior citizen. It will also focus on the maintenance of parental figures and their welfare, and also the parents' reliance on young ones in their later years. The importance of the interaction between law and other behavioural sciences, as well as people, social values, and social institutions, is highlighted in this study. The aged and senior citizens in our community, as well as old age establishments, have all aided me in understanding how a childless parent might seek upkeep from a relative who owns or will inherit the senior citizen's assets. And how the provincial government has set up maintenance commissions to determine on the amount of maintenance to be paid.”

-----GAZALA NOOR*

I. Introduction

The provision of care and protection for parents and the elderly is highly valued in Indian society. Because extremely old people, due to their diminished mobility and crippling infirmities, require other people to do things for them, the decline of the joint family structure has significantly to the issues experienced by older people. Apart from the increase of nuclear families in society and the decrease in the number of youngsters, the care of older people in families is deteriorating. As a result, more nursing professionals with the necessary abilities are needed to meet the demands of the elderly.¹

¹ Elderly India, Central Statistics Office Ministry of Statistics and Programme Implementation Government of India available at www.mospi.gov.in 2016, last visited 10 december 2021

Furthermore, it is the natural approach to identify old age through progressive changes in appearances such as greying hair, tooth loss, sagging skins, wrinkles, and loss of sensing functions. Not only that, but ageing is a lifelong process that includes physical, social, psychological, and spiritual changes from birth to death. Although aging is an on-going process yet the value of aging is seen differently at different points in the process and it occurs naturally in the human life cycle. It is the decline in the capacity of the functioning of the organs of human body. The population of the aged has been increasing over the years. The estimated population growth rate of elderly increased to 10 crores as per 2015 census reports i.e. 8.6 per cent of the total population.²

II. Elderly in India

India has the world's second-largest population of elderly people. This resulted in several social, economic, and political issues. The number of older people is expected to rise in the next years, yet our society lacks the fundamental competence to assist and respond to their needs. They are our society's most vulnerable group. The old are the ones who suffer the most in a society where cleanliness, sanitation, and universal healthcare are inadequate.

In addition to it the changes in the civil society is associated with modernity weakening the traditional values and family support systems for senior citizens (above the age of 60 years). Basic necessities such as nutrition, clothes, housing, and other necessities are required for a person to live a decent life. A man's moral obligation is to offer the aforementioned luxuries to his wife, parents, and children in the form of maintenance and so on. In addition, the frequency of elder abuse is on the rise, as is the difficulty in obtaining proper care and assistance. The issues of the elderly were also examined throughout the colonial period, although not as a separate class. They made several initiatives that were primarily for the sake of social security. Under the code of criminal procedure, maintenance is the process of maintaining or preserving for the maintenance of parents.³

Today's older individuals are compelled to live alone and face a variety of issues, including a lack of physical, social, emotional, and financial support. Therefore to overcome such difficulties and to face new challenges, the Government of India enacted the new legislation i.e: The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007⁴ in

² Chandramouli C. Census of India 2011 Registrar General & Census Commissioner, *India. Ministry of Home Affairs. 2013*

³ section-125Cr.P.C (Section 125 Criminal Procedure Code, 1973 was enacted to provide an effective remedy for the neglected persons to seek maintenance.)

⁴ Act No. 56 of 2007

the fifty-eighth year of Republic so as to provide maintenance and protection to parents and senior citizens. Importantly there is mandatory legal provisions to protect the rights of the senior citizens and to provide them care and support by the family and other stakeholders. Consequently being the signatory for the “Madrid International Plan of Action on Ageing, 2002,” several countries, including India, have introduced legislation for the social protection of senior citizens.⁵

In India, Senior Citizens is defined as ‘any citizens of India who has attained the age of sixty years or above’⁶. Basically there is a law to give them social security. It includes parents as well as other senior citizens. However this is special legislation and to implement the scheme and to achieve the objective of law, a tribunal has to be established in every state under the Act.⁷ However in 2007, The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, was passed providing provisions for the maintenance to support elderly parents and senior citizens. Hence, parents can claim maintenance either under section 125⁸ or under the Act, 2007.⁹ This Act makes claiming regular inspection for parents and older persons simple and quick. It imposes duties on children to support their parents/grandparents, as well as on relatives of senior persons to support such senior individuals. The major attractiveness of the Act of 2007, is that it includes protections to safeguard such people's lives and property. It also calls for the establishment of old age institutions to care for poor older adults and parents. The different aspects of the Act, 2007¹⁰ enumerates that, Senior citizens, including parents, who are unable to support themselves from their own earnings or from property held by them, are entitled to relief, and their children/grandchildren are obligated to support their parents, either father, mother, or both. Even family are obligated to take after the elderly. If such a child or relative fails to support his parents or senior citizens, the parents/senior citizens may seek the aid of a tribunal established under this Act to execute the maintenance remedy. Such parents/senior citizens may file an application with the tribunal, requesting support and other reliefs from their children/relatives. In this regard the Indian Government has taken several initiatives to deal with the issue of the increasing number of the grey population. Even before independence,

⁵ Issac TS, Ramesh A, Reddy SS, Sivakumar PT., Kumar CN. and Math SB. Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act 2007: A Critical Appraisal. *Indian J Psychol Med.* 2021;43(5S):107S–112S

⁶ *Id.*, section 2(h).

⁷ *Id.*, section 7.

⁸ Sec.125 Code of criminal procedure, 1973

⁹ The maintenance and welfare of parents and sr. citizen Act, 2007.

¹⁰ *supra* 9

the Adarkar Commission¹¹ has prepared a report these issues. Article 41¹² also calls on the government to make adequate provisions for the old, the sick, and the disabled. Furthermore, despite the fact that the national policy on older persons has many provisions for older people, it is still purely a policy document, even after 13 years of development. Due to a lack of legal provisions, it has not been enforced. Programs and projects for the welfare and empowerment of older people have remained reliant on the goodwill and wishes of those who feel compelled to help them.

In the end, this just serves to incite violations of elderly people's human rights.¹³ But the Act provides for more effective provisions for the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens by their children and relatives who inherit the property of the aged and also applies to the people of whole of India.

III. Aspects of aging

Growing old is a continual process that encompasses complicated physical changes to the body, redefinitions of social identities, and changes in psychological functioning. Actual age has little meaning on its own, but it may be used to predict physiological responses as well as changes in social standing.

Ageing is often defined by three factors that are inextricably linked to one another. They are as follows: (i) physiological ageing, (ii) psychological ageing, and (iii) social ageing.

a. Physiological ageing

It is a natural mechanism through which a person's body ages. It is distinguished by physical and mental changes observed in an ageing individual. The decline phase replaces the growth period that a person experiences in his or her earlier years. The changes that occur in physiological ageing are visible and easily recognisable in the outward physical attributes by creases in the skin, turning white of the body hair, dentures falling out, and so on; however, changes occur within the body as well. The functioning of the body's major organs has generally deteriorated, impacting the immune system, central nervous system (cns, digestive system, neurological system, endocrine system, reproductive functions, skeletal system, respiratory system, and so on.

¹¹ supra 3

¹² The Constitution of India

¹³ Agewell Research & Advocacy Centre; "Study on legal provisions and practices With Special Focus on Human rights on old people; Agewell Foundation, Elderly Lonely & Neglected study," *Helpage India Research & Development Journal* (2012)

b. psychological ageing

According to the World Health Organization, "greater lifespan without improved quality of life is a worthless reward."¹⁴ Ageing is a complicated process that entails decline, particularly at the psychological level of a person's capabilities. Personality, motivation, coping skills, adaptability, cognition, IQ, and mental health difficulties are all characteristics of psychological ageing. In terms of psychological functioning with age, life experiences are important to the person's functioning as well as wellbeing. It is plainly obvious that persons with meaningful lives have pretty decent psychological functioning.

That is to say, a person's social integration, engagement with society, and the roles he accepts and tries to play in his life, as well as his social connections, life circumstances, and personal traits, all have an impact on a person's psychological end up making, which has a significant impact on psychological functional ability, even when in old age. However, when sickness and infirmity affects the elderly, their capacity to live freely and participate in social activities declines, resulting in a greater feeling of isolation and discontent with their existence. social ageing

c. social ageing

Changes in a person's duties and connections, both within their network of relatives and friends and in formal organisations such as the workplace, are referred to as social ageing. Though social ageing varies from person to person, the perception of ageing as seen by the culture in which an individual lives plays an important impact. Individuals' social ageing experiences will be more positive and joyful in a society that sees ageing favourably than in a culture that views ageing negatively.

The social circumstances of such events impact individuals' and society's responses to ageing. These circumstances influence the importance, meaning, and perception of the ageing experience for people and communities alike. Individuals, in turn, jointly construct contexts. Significant changes in family and generational structures, job and retirement patterns, and biological processes affecting lifetime and obsolescence influence vulnerability and resilience in the ageing population and alter the contours of wellbeing.

¹⁴ The World Health Report 1997 - Conquering Suffering, Enriching Humanity, <http://www.who.int/whr/1997/en/last> visited on 26 may 2022.

Demographic, socioeconomic, social, and healthcare developments all have an impact on the resources accessible to an older population as well as the assets that ageing people may contribute to others.¹⁵

IV. AMENDMENT OF THE ACT, 2007

The Act was amended in 2019 to bring in key changes to improve Country's geriatric care and coverage. The following are the proposed changes in the amendment bill¹⁶ are as under below:-

- a. The definition of children has been broadened under the new law, Biological and adoptive sons, daughters, stepchildren, son-in-law and daughter-in-law, grandson and granddaughter, and legal guardians of minor children are all included in the new measure.
- b. Similarly, biological and adoptive father and mother, grandparents, father-in-law and mother-in-law are now included in the definition of parents.
- c. The phrase "maintenance" refers to the provision of food, clothing, housing, safety and security, medical attendance, healthcare, and treatment that are required for the parents to live a dignified life. The 2007 law defined maintenance as merely providing food, clothing, a place to live, and medical care and treatment.
- d. The measure proposes to remove the \$10,000 monthly maintenance cap, which is a significant change. The previous maximum limit was set at \$10,000 per month in the 2007 act. Senior folks may receive more than the sum if the amendment bill is ratified and signed into law.
- e. The tribunal in charge of these matters, on the other hand, would take into account the parent's or senior citizen's way of living, as well as their earnings and the earnings of their children or the person responsible. While the 2007 act compels the children to pay the maintenance amount within 30 days of the tribunal's order, the proposed amendment bill wants to shorten that period to 15 days.

¹⁵ National Research Council, *New Directions in the Sociology of Aging*, Panel on New Directions in Social Demography, Social Epidemiology and the Sociology of Aging. L.J. Waite and T.J. Plewes, Editors. Committee on Population, Division of Behavioral and Social Sciences and Education. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. (2013) p-15 http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK179089/pdf/Bookshelf_NBK179089.pdf last visited 27th may 2022.

¹⁶ The Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens (AMENDMENT) Bill, 2019 *A Bill further to amend the Maintenance and Welfare of Parents and Senior Citizens Act, 2007*

f. Children who forsake their parents, as defined by the bill, face a prison sentence of three to six months and a fine of up to Rs 10,000, or both, according to the amendment bill.

V. Significance of study

The notion of maintenance, as it has been performed in India since ancient times, takes on a comprehensive dimension, as it encompasses not only the supply of basic essentials for life sustenance related to the physical part of maintenance, as well as the social support and care that is discernibly needed most in old age.

The ancient value of kindred among members of the family and beyond, which has existed in India from ancient times, has been imprinted in the culture and its people. In India, every parent wishes for a male child. This urge to have a male kid is fueled by a desire to maintain the family lineage, as well as the fact that the son receives family property and has a claim to succession. Furthermore, the male kid not only succeeds his father in terms of succession and inherit, but also assumes control of the family. Administering the family affairs include looking after his elderly parents, wife, children, and other extended family members.

Even after the traditional family structure was dismantled, values still remain in the modern Indian family. This is why most parents choose to remain with their sons as they grow older. It's critical to put the sort of maintenance that every parent in India expects into context at this stage. Indian parents yearn to become a part of their son's family. Because parents spend their entire lives creating a respectable living for their family, they expect to be looked for and not considered as a burden. The majority of the money gained is used to educate the children and provide them with the necessities of life to the best of their ability. Marriage expenditures in India deplete a family's savings and, in some cases, put them into debt. With the money acquired during the productive years spent exclusively on the children, the parents enter old age with little to rely on but the love and devotion of their offspring. Parents have a right to expect their offspring to assume responsibility for them and give them with the care and assistance they require in their latter years. It is now the children's duty to look after their parents as a gesture of appreciation for the life they have been given.

The Maintenance and welfare of Parents and senior citizens Act, is a piece of legislation that makes it permissible for children and heirs to grant monthly allowances to senior citizens and parents. It also provides a simple, quick, and low-cost technique for the protection of elderly people's lives and possessions. It also permits State Government to

establish old age homes in every district. The Senior citizens who are unable to maintain themselves shall have the right to apply to Maintenance Tribunal seeking monthly allowance from their children or heirs.

Indian Journal of Contemporary
Legal and Social Issues